

Speculation on the Mathematical Meaning of the Norm of the Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 1, 2024

It is known that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ for a particle moving with constant speed. The more general form is: $P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)|$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. One sees immediately that in the constant v case, $P(x) = 1/L$ for all v and $-v$ pairs and all p and $-p$ pairs, where v is speed and p momentum. Given that $p = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ etc, we decide to use p as a variable of interest. In such a case, it is proportional to physical impulse. We ask: Is there mathematical meaning to the value $P(x) = 1/L$ given that it carries no direct information about all of the p (momenta) with which it is associated? Another way to phrase this question is to ask: Why is p information missing from $P(x) = 1/L$.

We suggest that in linear algebra, the quantity magnitude gives the semblance of loss of information. For example, given (x, y, z) , one knows each co-ordinate, but given $r = \sqrt{xx + yy + zz}$, one only knows the magnitude. Thus, mathematically, if one sees a constant r , one knows that there are many associated (x, y, z) vectors. We suggest that $P(x) = 1/L$ is also a magnitude associated with all $\pm p$ values. For a magnitude, one has components and rotational invariance. This suggests at minimum two components of a $P_d(p)$ probability, i.e. (P_{d1}, P_{d2}) such that $P_{d1}P_{d1} + P_{d2}P_{d2} = 1/L$. We next suggest that $P_d(p_1)P_d(p_2) = P_d(p_1 + p_2)$. These two conditions are satisfied by $\exp(ip)$, but for a given p , there is no running variable. We suggest that given that p represents linear motion in x (through v), that x should be part of the angle measure. In other words, one may generalize to $\exp(ipx)$. This suggests that for a large p , a small x leads to $px = 2\pi \cdot 3.14$. In other words, large p are associated with many x_j points yielding $px_j = 2\pi \cdot 3.14 n$, where n is an integer. We suggest that conservation of p is linked with conservation of x_j information along L . x_j information should be associated with entropy and so we suggest that p conservation is like a constant x_j information entropy.

$P(x)dx = dx/L$ and the Notion of Magnitude

We note that for constant motion, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length. This applies to motion to the right and left and holds for all speeds and momenta. Probability is based on the idea that a particle spends the same amount of time in each fixed dt . Different speeds, however, represent different dt values and so $P(x)$ just represents the relative time in each dx . In other words, a lot of information is missing. It seems that one should be able to distinguish between p or v values, but $P(x) = 1/L$ does not do this.

We suggest asking the question: Does $P(x) = 1/L$, which excludes details about p values, represent a mathematical object which justifies the apparent loss of this information? We suggest that the modulus of linear algebra does exactly the following. In fact, the modulus set equal to $1/L$ becomes a constraint.

In order to have a modulus, however, one needs components and so we suggest a:

$P_d(p) = \text{dynamical probability} = (P_{d1}, P_{d2})$ with two as the minimally acceptable number of dimensions ((1))

such that: $Pd_1Pd_1 + Pd_2Pd_2 = 1$ ((2))

We further suggest that $Pd(p_1)Pd(p_2) = Pd(p_1+p_2)$ ((3))

In order to have components, however, one requires a dynamic variable and p is constant. We use p instead of v because $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc and p represents a physical impulse.

Given that p is associated with motion in x , we suggest that this must be the dynamical variable. This suggest a periodic motion of:

$Pd(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ (((4)) as a solution of ((1)), ((2)) and ((3))

This means that:

$1 = \exp(i px_j)$ for $px_j = 2\pi n$, where n is an integer ((5))

Thus, a large p has a small wavelength proportional to $1/p$. ((6)). As a result, one does not only have a set of vectors associated with a given p , but there is two-handedness, i.e. clockwise and counterclockwise rotation which maps directly to p and $-p$ and there is a different frequency for different p values, yet all have the same magnitude $P(x)=1/L$.

We suggest that p seems to be associated with information in the sense that for a given L , ((5)) implies that a large p is related to more information about x points than a small one. Furthermore, a large p is associated with a large energy. This seems to follow from the idea that a large p may be subdivided into a sum of many small p values. In terms of $Pd(px)$, this means that $Pd(p\text{-large}, x) = Pd(p_1,x) Pd(p_2,x)$ etc., where all p_j are positive. This seems to suggest that as one increases p , one increases information about x , i.e. $px_j = 2\pi n$ points.

If one considers that information is conserved then it seems that this is associated with conservation of momentum. In other words, there may be an informational association of one variable (x) with a physical conservation of another variable (p). It seems that this information, in turn, may be associated with a kind of entropy. Thus, conservation of momentum from an informational standpoint might be similar to stating that entropy does not change. For example, it is known that:

$\int \exp(-ip_1x - ip_2x) \exp(ip_3x + ip_4x) dx = \delta(p_1+p_2, p_3,p_4)$ ((6))

One may think of p_1+p_2 as a wavelength or information and argue that one cannot have a change in this information unless there is a function, such as $V(x)$ which may change information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that $P(x)dx=dx/L$ makes no reference to any $p, -p$ value or $v, -v$ value. We ask: Is there a mathematical value which seems to “lose” information? We argue that the modulus from linear algebra does just this. Thus, we suggest that $P(x)=1/L$ is a modulus associated with all $p, -p$ sets. We use p instead of v , because $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc and is proportional to impulse. If this is the case, we consider $Pd(p) = (Pd_1, Pd_2)$ such that $Pd_1Pd_1+Pd_2Pd_2=1/L$ as the simplest solution, We also suggest that $Pd(p_1)Pd(p_2)=Pd(p_1=p_2)$. There must, however, be a running variable and we suggest that this is x because motion occurs in x . These ideas seem to lead to: $Pd(p,x)= \exp(ipx)$.

We note that this approach associates a constant p with a set of x_j points such that $p x_j = 2*3.14 n$, where n is an integer. If one fixes L , then a large p (large energy) is associated with many x_j points. We note that p is a conserved quantity in mechanics and suggest that this conservation is associated with the conservation of the information of x_j . We also suggest that the information of x_j is associated with an entropy and conservation of p may be described in terms of a conservation of information entropy associated with a different variable, namely x . X is not just any variable, but is the running variable linked with p . For L_z (z -component of angular momentum), θ is the running variable. For energy, the running variable is t because energy (e.g. a rest mass) does not need to change dynamically.